

Angelo Leogrande^{1*}[°]

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

[°]LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Air Quality in the Italian Regions

Between 2010 and 2021 it decreased on average by an amount equal to -24.04%

Istat calculates the value of air quality in the Italian regions. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2010 and 2021. Air quality is defined as the percentage of valid measurements higher than the reference value for health defined by the WHO (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), out of the total measurements valid annual average PM2.5 concentrations for all station types (urban and suburban traffic, urban industrial and urban and suburban, rural background).

Ranking of the Italian regions by air quality value in 2021. Trentino Alto Adige and Veneto are in first place for air quality value with a value of 100, followed by Lombardy with an amount of 97.1 unit. In the middle of the table is Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to 75 units, followed by Tuscany with an amount equal to 73.5 units and Puglia with a value equal to 69.2 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a value of 50.00 units, followed by Basilicata with a value of 8.3 units, and Sardinia with a value of 6.1.

Ranking of the Italian regions by air quality value between 2010 and 2021. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place for percentage change in air quality between 2010 and 2021 with a corresponding value of 10.01%. to a variation from an amount of 90.9 units up to a value of 100 units. Veneto follows with a percentage variation of 3.31% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 96.8 units up to a value of 100 units. Lombardy is in third place with a variation equal to an amount of -2.9% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 100 units up to a value of 97.1 units. In the middle of the table is Campania with a value of -20.6% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 100 units in 2010 up to a value of 79.4 units in 2021. Valle d'Aosta follows with a variation equal to -25.00% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 100 units up to a value of 75 units. Calabria follows with a variation equal to -25.04% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 66.7 units up to a value of 50 units. Umbria closes the ranking with a value of -42.9% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 100 units up to a value of 57.1 units. Molise follows with a variation equal to an amount of -42.9 units corresponding to a variation from an amount of 100 up to a value of 57.1 units. Molise follows with a value equal to -43.76% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 88.9 units up to a value of 50 units between 2010 and 2021. Sardinia closes the ranking with a variation equal to one amount of -91.96% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 75.9 units in 2010 up to a value of 6.1 units in 2021. Overall the average value of air quality decreased by -24.04% or from a value of 89 units in 2010 up to a value of 67.6 in 2021.

Italian macro-regions. The value of air quality decreased significantly in all Italian macro-regions between 2010 and 2021. In particular, air quality decreased in the North with an amount equal to -9.33%, in the North- West with an amount equal to -6.11%, in the North-East with a value equal to -11.89%, in the Center with a value equal to -29.50%, in the South with a value equal to -34, 28%, in Southern Italy with a value of -26.13%, in the Islands with a value of -48.28%.

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Friuli Venezia Giulia, Piedmont, Puglia, Campania, Abruzzo, Emilia Romagna, Trentino Alto Adige, Lombardy, Veneto, Liguria, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Lazio, Marche, Molise, Calabria;
- Cluster 2: Basilicata, Sicily, Sardinia.

We can see that cluster 1 is dominant compared to cluster 2. However, since cluster 1 is composed of a very heterogeneous set of regions we believe that clustering is essentially inefficient for a value of $k=2$. Therefore we have a value of $k=3$. Therefore, setting a value of $k=3$ results in the following clusters:

- Cluster 1: Lombardy, Piedmont, Puglia, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Campania, Trentino Alto Adige, Abruzzo, Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Umbria.
- Cluster 2: Basilicata and Sardinia;
- Cluster 3: Calabria, Sicily, Molise, Marche, Tuscany, Lazio.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters, the following value results: $C1 > C3 > C2$. Therefore it appears that the air quality value is substantially high in the Central-Northern regions, while on the contrary the air quality is reduced in the southern regions.

Conclusions. The value of air quality decreased in all Italian macro-regions by an average amount of 24.04%. The comparison between 2010 and 2021 highlights the reduction in air quality in all Italian macro-regions. The condition of the South is particularly serious. The data tends to be counterfactual. In fact, it is common opinion that the Po Valley is characterized by high levels of pollution. On the contrary, from the clustering analysis it appears that the regions that have the highest levels of air quality are precisely the northern regions. The southern regions are characterized by low levels of air quality.

References

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Leogrande, D., & Anobile, F. (2023). Beds in Health Facilities in the Italian Regions: A Socio-Economic Approach. Available at SSRN 4577029.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(11), 166-187.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., De Cristoforo, G., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Sales Growth Nexus in Europe. Available at SSRN 3933407.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in europe. Available at SSRN 3956755.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN 4021150.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN 4010098.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. Available at SSRN 3971174.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The smes innovation in europe. Available at SSRN 3964059.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-friendly environment in europe. Available at SSRN 3933553.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate (No. 108). Money and Finance Research group (Mo. Fi. R.)-Univ. Politecnica Marche-Dept. Economic and Social Sciences.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. Discover Global Society, 2(1), 1-20.

Appendix

Air Quality in the Italian Regions												
Regione	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Piemonte	95,8	96,2	92,6	97,1	94,7	94,7	92,5	94,9	94,4	88,6	94,3	87,5
Valle d'Aosta	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	33,3	100	75
Liguria	93,8	100	90,5	81,8	85,7	100	91,7	91,7	95,8	84,6	67,9	56,7
Lombardia	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	98,5	100	97	97	97,1
Trentino-Alto Adige	90,9	90,9	92,9	92,9	92,9	91,7	91,7	91,7	91,7	83,3	91,7	100
Veneto	96,8	97,5	100	100	96,8	100	97	100	97	100	100	100
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	100	100	95,8	100	91,3	92,6	88	92,3	89,3	89,3	85,7	88
Emilia-Romagna	98,1	96,1	91,5	89,1	91,3	91,5	89,4	89,4	89,4	89,4	89,4	87,2
Toscana	90,7	90,3	86,1	91,3	84,6	86,7	78,8	79,4	79,4	76,5	76,5	73,5
Umbria	100	100	95	85,7	86,4	90,9	86,4	72,7	90	76,2	76,2	57,1
Marche	90,5	90,9	100	100	61,5	76,9	61,5	83,3	83,3	76,5	66,7	53,3

Lazio	92	93,1	94,4	91,9	86,5	89,5	85	72	75,5	71,4	68	66
Abruzzo	100	100	100	100	100	100	85,7	80	90,9	77,8	81,8	81,8
Molise	88,9	88,9	77,8	100	100	100	60	100	66,7	33,3	33,3	50
Campania	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	85,7	84	77,4	89,3	79,4
Puglia	95,7	100	96	90,9	94,7	97,9	91,5	95,6	97,9	92	83	69,2
Basilicata	14,3	40	40	55,6	100	66,7	50	40	70	60	40	8,3
Calabria	66,7	60	75	100	100	89,5	75	70	80	80	40	50
Sicilia	90	88,9	78,6	63	92,3	68,4	65	42,9	69,6	68,2	50	66
Sardegna	75,9	65,8	60,5	48,7	50	52,5	42,5	45	57,6	37,5	30,3	6,1

Air Quality in the Italian Regions					
Rank	Regione	2010	2021	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Trentino-Alto Adige	90,9	100	9,1	10,01

2	Veneto	96,8	100	3,2	3,31
3	Lombardia	100	97,1	-2,9	-2,9
4	Piemonte	95,8	87,5	-8,3	-8,66
5	Emilia-Romagna	98,1	87,2	-10,9	-11,11
	Friuli-Venezia				
6	Giulia	100	88	-12	-12
7	Abruzzo	100	81,8	-18,2	-18,2
8	Toscana	90,7	73,5	-17,2	-18,96
9	Campania	100	79,4	-20,6	-20,6
10	Valle d'Aosta	100	75	-25	-25
11	Calabria	66,7	50	-16,7	-25,04
12	Sicilia	90	66	-24	-26,67
13	Puglia	95,7	69,2	-26,5	-27,69
14	Lazio	92	66	-26	-28,26
15	Liguria	93,8	56,7	-37,1	-39,55
16	Marche	90,5	53,3	-37,2	-41,1
17	Basilicata	14,3	8,3	-6	-41,96
18	Umbria	100	57,1	-42,9	-42,9
19	Molise	88,9	50	-38,9	-43,76
20	Sardegna	75,9	6,1	-69,8	-91,96
	Average	89	67,6	-21,4	-24,04

Air Quality in the Italian Macro-Regions												
	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Nord	97,5	97,5	95,6	95,1	94,5	96,3	94	94,8	94,8	91,2	91,1	88,4
Nord-ovest	98,2	99,1	96,4	95,8	95,9	98,4	96,2	96,2	97,7	90,8	90,3	92,2
Nord-est	96,7	96,4	94,8	94,3	93	94,2	91,5	93,3	91,7	91,7	92	85,2
Centro	92,2	93,1	92,6	90,9	82,7	87,4	80,6	75,4	80	74,4	71,7	65
Mezzogiorno	84,6	82,4	77,9	74,7	81,7	81,2	69,9	69,5	79,8	73,4	61,8	55,6
Sud	86,5	88,3	86,7	90,5	98,3	94,3	82,3	82,8	88	81,3	72,3	63,9
Isole	81,6	75,4	67,6	54,5	66,7	57,6	50	44,3	62,5	52,2	37,3	42,2

